

Lepidoptera fauna of Kemerovo Region: Lasiocampoidea and Bombycoidea

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Abstract

Thirty six species from 5 families (Lasiocampidae, Brahmaeidae, Endromididae, Saturniidae, Sphingidae) of Lasiocampoidea and Bombycoidea superfamilies are reported from the territory of Kemerovo Region of Russia. Nine species – *Malacosoma castrense* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Eriogaster lanestris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Macrothylacia rubi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Phyllodesma japonicum* Leech, 1889, *Dendrolimus pini* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Odonestis pruni* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lemonia dumii* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Agrius convolvuli* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Proserpinus proserpina* (Pallas, 1772) – are new to Kemerovo Region.

Keywords

Fauna, Lepidoptera, Lasiocampoidea, Bombycoidea, West Siberia, Kemerovo Region

Introduction

The fauna of moths of the Kemerovo Region has been studied extremely fragmentally. Several works, starting from the beginning of the XX century, provide the

data on Bombycoïd Lepidoptera (Tshugunov 1916; Vnukovsky 1926; Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2019; 2020; Shchetinina 2023a; 2023b). In addition, 4 species from two families are listed in the Red Book of Kuzbass (2021).

Based on original collections and analysis of literary data, in the proposed article we publish a list of Lepidoptera from the superfamilies Lasiocampoidea and Bombycoidea of the Kemerovo Region.

Materials and methods

The nomenclature and systematic position of taxa in the text are given in accordance with the catalogue of Lepidoptera of Russia (Sinev 2019). The distribution of species is given according to literary sources (Zolotuhin 2015; Zolotuhin and Evdoshenko 2019). All specimens are deposited in private collections of Alexey Korschunov (AKK, Kemerovo, Russia), Vladimir Polevod (VPK, Kemerovo, Russia), Vadim Ivonin (VIN, Novosibirsk, Russia) and Alexander Kostyunin (AEK, Kemerovo, Russia). Species firstly reported for the territory of Kemerovo Region are marked by asterisk. The map was prepared using the Google-Earth program (Fig. 1). Localities were imported into it from a csv-file. The numbers on the map correspond to the ordinal numbers of the locations in the list below.

Geographical coordinates of the collecting sites:

1. Aleksandrovka – Kemerovsky District, Aleksandrovka village vicinity, 55°21'20.4"N 86°19'20.5"E;
2. Azhendarovo – Krapivinsky District, 8 km SSW of Saltymakovo village, Azhendarovo research biological station, 54°45'20.6"N 87°01'40.4"E (Fig. 5);
3. Bekovo – Belovo town District, 4 km S of Bekovo village, 54°19'40.7"N 86°12'44.7"E (Fig. 3);
4. Berezovo – Novokuznetsky District, Berezovo village vicinity, 53°42'52.4"N 86°48'38.8"E;
5. Karyer – Yashkinsky district, Karyer village, 55°49'44.61"N, 85°28'7.64"E;
6. Kedrovka – Kemerovsky District, Kedrovka District, Kedrovsky coal mine, 55°31'51.8"N 86°04'00.3"E;
7. Kemerovo – Kemerovo, Leninsky District, Kuzbass botanical garden, 55°21'57.7"N 86°11'32.6"E;
8. Kiselevsk – Kiselevsk town, 53°59'24.4"N, 86°31'10.2"E;
9. Kolmogorovo – Yashkinsky District, Kolmogorovo village, 55°38'18.60"N, 85°39'42.29"E;
10. Krasnoselka – Yashkinsky District, Krasnoselka village, 55°52'0.46"N, 85°13'4.89"E;
11. Krasnoye – Kemerovo, Krasnoye Lake, 55°21'44.5"N, 86°08'59.6"E;

12. Mazurovo – Kemerovsky District, Mazurovo village, 55°19'12.5"N, 85°54'14.7"E;

13. Metallploshchadka – Kemerovsky District, Metallploshchadka village, 55°19'16.0"N 86°11'53.0"E;

14. Mikhailovka – Prokopyevsky district, Mikhailovka village, 54° 2'53.00"N, 86°21'23.00"E;

15. Morkovkino – Yashkinsky district, Morkovkino village, 55°42'25.20"N, 85°36'57.60"E;

16. Mozzhukha – Kemerovsky District, Mozzhukha village, 55°25'46.2"N, 85°54'20.7"E;

17. Okunevo – Promyshlennovsky District, Okunevo village, 54°55'39.8"N 85°24'14.1"E;

18. Orbita – Topkinsky District, Orbita gardens, 55°14'57"N 85°45'57"E;

19. Osinovka – Kemerovsky District, Osinovka village, 55°24'43.7"N, 86°17'23.6"E (Fig. 2);

20. Pacha – Yashkinsky District, Pacha village, 55°42'21.59"N, 85°29'48.29"E;

21. Pashkovo – Yashkinsky District, Pashkovo village, 56°03'14.4"N, 85°08'06.1"E;

22. Podyakovo – Kemerovsky District, Podyakovo village, 55°34'42,8"N 85°49'46,7"E;

23. Salair – border of the Novosibirsk and Kemerovo Regions, Salair mountain ridge, valley of the Istok River, 54°46'40,8"N 84°56'58,3"E (Fig. 8);

24. Sheregesh – Tashtagol'sky District, 4 km N of Sheregesh village, Zelenaya mountain, 52°57'12.1"N, 87°57'12.1"E;

25. Shestakovo – Tshebulinsky District, Shestakovo village, 55°53'26.0"N 87°57'32.2"E (Fig. 4);

26. Shorokhovo – Novokuznetsky District, Shorokhovo village vicinity, Tishinsky protected area, 53°57'14.1"N 87°15'44.6"E (Fig. 6);

27. Tanaev pond – border of the Novosibirsk and Kemerovo Regions, W bank of Tanaev pond, 54°46'48.16"N, 84°58'47.43"E (Fig. 9);

28. Teben'kovka – Kemerovsky District, Teben'kovka village vicinity, 55°21'18.9"N, 86°21'56.1"E;

29. Tomskaya Pisanitsa – Yashkinsky District, Tomskaya Pisanitsa museum-reserve, 55°39'46.3"N 85°37'29.1"E;

30. Ust'-Naryk – Novokuznetsky District, Ust'-Naryk village vicinity, 54°20'06.1"N 87°26'27.3"E;

31. Verkhnyaya Ters' – Novokuznetsky District, Kuznetsky Alatau, "Verkhnyaya Ters'" guarding point, Verkhnyaya Ters' River bank, 54°10'35"N 88°07'19"E;

32. Yashkino – Yashkinsky district, Yashkino village, 55°52'24.00"N, 85°25'35.00"E;

33. Zayachya Gora – Promyshlennovsky District, SE bank of Tanaev pond, 54°45'39.88"N, 85°01'05.98"E (Fig. 7).

Figure 1. Map of collecting localities in Kemerovo Region.

Result

Annotated check list

Lasiocampoidea

Lasiocampidae

Poecilocampa populi (Linnaeus, 1758)

References: Izersky 1999.

Material examined. 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 18.09.2023, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 1 spm., Pacha, at light, 10.10.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic species. From Western Europe to Baikal Lake and Amur Region.

***Trichiura crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

References: Tshugunov 1916.

Material examined. 1 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 18-30.07.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 25 spm., Ust`-Naryk, at light, 7-8.08.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 14-16.08.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 12.08.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 7 spm., Pacha, at light, 16-17.08.2019, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species distributed from Western Europe to Amur Region.

****Malacosoma castrense* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig.10

Material examined. 1 spm., Yashkino, at light, 9-10.07.2019, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species distributed from Western Europe to Primorye Territory with a gap in Eastern Siberia.

****Eriogaster lanestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 1 larva, Zayachya Gora, 15.06.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

***Lasiocampa quercus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

References: Tshugunov 1916.

Material examined. 1 spm., Azhendarovo, 20.06.-20.07.2010, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Berezovo, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 5 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 16.06.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); Zayachya Gora, at light, 24.06.2020, 28.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration).

Distribution. Euro-Siberian species, distributed from Europe to Baikal Lake, also this species known from Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan.

***Pachygastris trifolii* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)**

References: Izersky 1999 (as *Lasiocampa trifolii* L.).

Distribution. Euro-Siberian species, distributed from Europe to Baikal Lake, also on Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenia, North-West China.

**Macrothylacia rubi* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. 1 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15.06.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Pashkovo, at light, 14-17.06.2003, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 6 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 17-19.06.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 6 spm., Orbita, at light, 19.05.2022, 26.05.2022, 4.06.2023, D.A. Efimov (AKK); 2 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 15.05.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 5 spm., Yashkino, at light, 6.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Pacha, 8.06.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species. Widespread from Western Europe to Russian Far East, North-East China and Mongolia.

Euthrix potatoria (Linnaeus, 1758)

References: Izersky 1999 (as *Philudoria patatoria* L.)

Material examined. 4 spm., Shestakovo, 13-15.07.2015, 21-30.06.2018, 15-30.06.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 8-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Azhendarovo, 20-24.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 14 spm., Mazurovo, 5-8.07.2019, S.V. Blinova (AKK); 4 spm., Mazurovo, 1-9.07.2019, V. Bystrova (AKK); 1 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 22-24.06.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 5 spm., Bekovo, at light, 10-12.07.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 11 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 18-19.06.2021, 1-2.07.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 4 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 12.07.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 5 spm., Krutoi, at light, 16.06.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Pacha, at light, 10.06.2014, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Morkovkino, at light, 15.06.2014, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species. Widely distributed from Western Europe to Japan.

Cosmotriche lobulina ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

References: Tshugunov 1916 (as *Selenephera lunigera* Esp.).

Material examined. 1 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 23-29.07.2017, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 21.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 3 spm., Yashkino, at light, 25.07.2015, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Kolmogorovo, at light, 3.08.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to Transbaikalia.

Gastropacha populifolia (Esper, 1784)

References: Izersky 1999.

Material examined. 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 3.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

***Gastropacha quercifolia* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

References: Izersky 1999.

Material examined. 1 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15.06.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Azhendarovo, 11-13.09.2015, 20-24.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 18-30.07.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 3 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 22-24.06.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 12.07.2020, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 3 spm., Mikhailovka, at light, 8.07.2023, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Yashkino, at light, 6.07.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

***Phylodesma ilicifolia* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig.11

References: Izersky 1999 (as *Epinaptera ilicifolia*)

Material examined. 1 spm., Yashkino, at light, 17-18.05.2015, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to Amur Region.

****Phylodesma japonicum* Leech, 1889**

Material examined. 1 spm., Salair, at light, 1.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN).

Distribution. From Europe through Siberia to the Far East.

****Dendrolimus pini* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 3 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 15.06.2021, 21.07.2021, 28.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN).

Distribution. From Western Europe to Southern Siberia and Transbaikalia.

***Dendrolimus superans sibiricus* Tschetverikov, 1908**

References: Vnukovsky 1926; Izersky 1999.

Material examined. 1 spm., Sheregesh, at light, 1-3.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 21-30.06.2018, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 21.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 6 spm., Yashkino, at light, 1.07.2016, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Subtranspalaeartic boreal species. Distributed from Eastern Europe to Far East.

Figures 2–9. 2 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Osinovka, 18.06.2007, photo by A.V. Korshunov; 3 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Bekovo, 20.06.2021, photo by A.V. Korshunov; 4 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Shestakovo, 26.07.2020, photo by A.V. Korshunov; 5 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Azhendarovo, 28.06.2017, photo by A.V. Korshunov; 6 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Shorokhovo, 14.08.2020, photo by A.V. Korshunov; 7 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Zayachya Gora, 15.09.2020, photo by V.V. Ivonin; 8 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Salair, 29.05.2022, photo by V.V. Ivonin; 9 – Habitats of Kemerovo Region: Tanaev Pond, 1.08.2021, photo by V.V. Ivonin.

****Odonestis pruni* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 1 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 14-16.08.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 11.08.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 2 spm., Yashkino, at light, 1.07.2016, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 1 spm., Yashkino, at light, 9.07.2006, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to South Siberia, Far East, China, Korea, Japan.

Bombycoidea**Brahmaeidae******Lemonia dumi* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Figs 12, 22

Material examined. 1 spm., Metallploshchadka, 9.09.2018, V.A. Polevod (VPK); 1 spm., Kedrovka, 20.09.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, 22.09.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN).

Distribution. From Europe to Baikal Lake.

Endromididae***Endromis versicolora* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Figs 24, 25

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2000.

Material examined. 1 spm., Teben`kovka, 15.05.2011, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 3 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 29.04.2017, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 16.05.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 4 spm., Pacha, 4-5.05.2014, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 5 spm., Yashkino, 8-9.05.2015, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 3 spm., Kolmogorovo, 10-11.05.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Saturniidae***Aglia tau* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 13

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2000.

Material examined. 1 spm., Osinovka, 16.05.1997, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Azhendarovo, 21-23.05.2011, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 3 spm., Tomskaya Pisanitsa, at light, 20-21.05.2022, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 15.05.2021, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 5 spm., Yashkino, at light, 16-17.05.2013, V.A.

Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Yashkino, at light, 10-11.06.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 7 spm., Pacha, 20.05.2020, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Eudia pavonia (Linnaeus, 1758)

Figs 14, 23

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2012.

Material examined. 1 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 12.05.2009, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Azhendarovo, 21-23.05.2011, A.V. Korshunov and A.E. Kostyunin (AKK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, 12-13.05.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Tomskaya Pisanitsa, 29-30.04.2022, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 4 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 30.04.2022, 17.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 15.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 1 spm., Salair, at light, 01.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (VIN); 3 spm., Yashkino, at light, 20-21.05.2015, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Yashkino, at light, 6.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 1 spm., Yashkino, at light, 17-18.05.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Sphingidae

Smerinthinae

Laothoe amurensis (Staudinger, 1892)

References: Izersky 1999; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 2 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15-20.07.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 7 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 16.07.2009, 1-20.07.2010, A.V. Korshunov, A.E. Kostyunin (AKK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 15-30.06.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Mazurovo, 8.07.2019, S.V. Blinova (AKK); 2 spm., Bekovo, at light, 10-12.07.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 17-19.06.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 22.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 3 spm., Kemerovo, 3-4.07.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Yashkino, 26.06.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Karyer, 10.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species. From Europe to Japan, also in Kazakhstan, Mongolia, NE China, Korea.

Laothoe populi (Linnaeus, 1758)

References: Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 1 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 15.06.1999, V.A. Polevod (AKK); 1 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15-20.07.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm.,

Azhendarovo, at light, 18.07.2009, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, 8-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Yashkino, 21.06.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 3 spm., Krasnoselka, 10-11.06.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 1 spm., Yashkino, 19-20.07.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to Baikal Lake.

***Smerinthus caecus* Ménériés, 1857**

References: Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 3 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15-20.07.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 3-10.07.2007, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Azhendarovo, 16.07.2009, 19.07.2010, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Shestakovo, 13-15.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 5 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 22-24.06.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Kemerovo, 1-2.07.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 6 spm., Pacha, 21-22.06.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 7 spm., Yashkino, 21-22.07.2014, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 3 spm., Kemerovo, 23.06.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

***Smerinthus ocellatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 15

References: Izersky 1999.

Material examined. 1 spm., Krasnoye, 24.06.2007, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK).

Distribution. Westpalaeartic species distributed from Europe, Caucasus, Turkey and Iran to Altai, Tyan-Shan, Mongolia.

***Mimas tiliae* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 26

References: Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 1 spm. Kemerovo, at light, 10.06.2004, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, 10.06.2011, M. Sinitsky (AKK); 1 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 8-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 13-15.07.2015, 21-30.06.2018, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 3 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 17-18.06.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Orbita, at light, 12.06.2022, D.A. Efimov (AKK); 10 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 16.06.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 12 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 24.06.2020, 12.07.2020, 11.08.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 5 spm., Kemerovo, 24-25.06.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Yashkino, 7-8.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to Altai.

Sphinginae

Sphinx ligustri Linnaeus, 1758

References: Tshugunov 1916; Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 2 spm., Osinovka, at light, 15.07.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 19.07.2010, 20-24.07.2015, A.E. Kostyunin, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 13-15.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Orbita, at light, 4.06.2023, D.A. Efimov (AKK); 2 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 16.06.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 7 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 24.06.2020, 12.07.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 2 spm., Mikhailovka, at light, 23-24.06.2019, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 3 spm., Yashkino, 29-30.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Pacha, at light, 14-15.06.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Hyloicus morio Rothschild & Jordan, 1903

Fig. 16

References: Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 3 spm., Podyakovo, at light, 3-10.07.2007, 9-10.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 24.06.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 2 spm., Yashkino, at light, 9-10.07.2013, 19-20.07.2013, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From West Siberia to Japan.

**Agrius convolvuli* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Fig. 17

Material examined. 1 spm., Teben`kovka, 17.08.2008, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK).

Distribution. Palaeartic, African, Oriental and Australian Regions.

Macroglossinae

Hemaris fuciformis (Linnaeus, 1758)

References: Red Book... 2000; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 2 spm., Bekovo, 30.05.2003, 30.05.2009, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Mozhukha, 10.06.2004, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Verkhnyaya Ters`, 9-11.07.2009, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Aleksandrovka, 6.06.2010, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, gardens, 12.07.2018, N. Korshunova (AKK); 1 spm., Mazurovo, 5-8.07.2019, S.V. Blinova (AKK); 10 spm., Mozhukha, 24.05.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, on *Sirynga* flowers, 28.05.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Kolmogorovo, 21.06.2016, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic species.

***Hemaris tityus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 18

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2012; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 1 spm., Bekovo, 30.05.2009, A.V. Korshunov (AKK).

Distribution. From Europe to Baikal Lake.

***Macroglossum stellatarum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 19

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2012; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 2 spm., Azhendarovo, 3.09.2011, A.V. Korshunov and A.E. Kostyunin (AKK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, 30.06.2021, S. Oplachko (AKK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic migrant species.

***Hyles euphorbiae* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Fig. 20

References: Izersky 1999; Red Book... 2012; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 1 spm., Mozzhukha, 11.08.2002, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Kiselevsk, ex larva, 24.08.2005, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 9 spm., Bekovo, at light, 10-12.07.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 4 spm., Okunevo, at light, 16.08.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 12.07.2020, 21.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration).

Distribution. From Europe to West Siberia and Kazakhstan. Introduced in USA and Canada.

***Hyles gallii* (Rottemburg, 1775)**

References: Izersky 1999; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 2 spm., Azhendarovo, 1.09.2011, 1.09.2012, A.E. Kostyunin, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 20-24.07.2015, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 25.07.2016, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 18-30.07.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Mazurovo, 4-8.07.2019, S.V. Blinova (AKK); 1 spm., Okunevo, at light, 16.08.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 2 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 16.06.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 2 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 12.07.2020, 21.07.2021, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 6 spm., Mikhailovka, at light, 25-26.06.2020, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 3 spm., Yashkino, at light, 9-10.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 2 spm., Yashkino, at light, 6.07.2011, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Deilephila elpenor (Linnaeus, 1758)

References: Izersky 1999; Ryzhkova 2020; Shchetinina 2023a.

Material examined. 1 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 6.06.1999, V.A. Polevod (VPK); 2 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 13-15.07.2015, 18-30.07.2019, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Azhendarovo, ex larva (larva 09.2011), imago 18.01.2012, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 1 spm., Bekovo, at light, 10-12.07.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 9 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 1-2.06.2021, 17-18.06.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Orbita, at light, 31.05.2022, D.A. Efimov (AKK); 2 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 21.07.2021, 11.08.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 5 spm., Yashkino, at light, 11-12.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. Transpalaeartic temperate species.

Choerocampa porcellus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Fig. 27

References: Izersky 1999; Shchetinina 2023a (as *Deilephila porcellus*)

Material examined. 1 spm., Mozhukha, 12.07.2001, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Aleksandrovka, 28.05.2011, A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 2 spm., Shestakovo, at light, 13-15.07.2015, 21-30.06.2018, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 4 spm., Shorokhovo, at light, 22-24.06.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Bekovo, at light, 10-12.07.2020, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 15 spm., Kemerovo, at light, 1-2.06.2021, 17-19.06.2021, 1-2.07.2021, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 9 spm., Tanaev pond, at light, 18.05.2020, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 7 spm., Zayachya Gora, at light, 11.08.2020, 28.05.2022, V.V. Ivonin (visual registration); 6 spm., Yashkino, at light, 9-10.06.2012, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Yashkino, at light, 3-4.07.2014, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 4 spm., Mikhailovka, at light, 4-5.07.2022, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to Baikal Lake and Mongolia.

**Proserpinus proserpina* (Pallas, 1772)

Fig. 21

Material examined. 1 spm., Aleksandrovka, on the road, 07.2006. A.E. Kostyunin (AEK); 1 spm., Azhendarovo, at light, 18.07.2009, A.V. Korshunov (AKK); 1 spm., Yashkino, at light, 30-31.05.2016, V.A. Akaev (VAK); 1 spm., Yashkino, on *Syringa* flowers, 27.05.2005, V.A. Akaev (VAK).

Distribution. From Europe to West Siberia, also in Middle East and Middle Asia, Kazakhstan, West and Southwest China.

Figures 10–21. 10 – Imago, general view: *Malacosoma castrense*, Yashkino, 9-10.07.2019, V.A. Akaev; 11 – Imago, general view: *Phyllodesma ilicifolia*, Yashkino, 17-18.05.2015, V.A. Akaev; 12 – Imago, general view: *Lemonia dumi*, Metallplohchadka, 9.09.2018, V.A. Polevod; 13 – Imago, general view: *Aglia tau*, Yashkino, 16-17.05.2014, V.A. Akaev; 14 – Imago, general view: *Eudia pavonia*, Yashkino, 20-21.05.2015, V.A. Akaev; 15 – Imago, general view: *Smerinthus ocellatus*, Krasnoye, 24.06.2007, A.E. Kostyunin; 16 – Imago, general view: *Hyloicus morio*, Yashkino, 19-20.07.2013, V.A. Akaev; 17 – Imago, general view: *Agrius convolvuli*, Teben`kovka, 24.06.2007, A.E. Kostyunin; 18 – Imago, general view: *Hemaris tityus*, Bekovo, 30.05.2009, A.V. Korshunov; 19 – Imago, general view: *Macroglossum stellatarum*, Kemerovo, 30.06.2021, S.S. Oplachko; 20 – Imago, general view: *Hyles euphorbiae*, Okunevo, 16.08.2021, A.V. Korshunov; 21 – Imago, general view: *Proserpinus proserpina*, Yashkino, 30-31.05.2016, V.A. Akaev.

Figures 22–27. 22 – Imago, photo in nature: *Lemonia dumi*, Zayachya Gora, 22.09.2021, photo by V.V. Ivonin; 23 – Imago, photo in nature: *Eudia pavonia*, Yashkino, 6.05.2021, photo by V.A. Akaev; 24 – Imago, photo in nature: *Endromis versicolora*, ♂, Kemerovo, 8.05.2023, photo by V.A. Akaev; 25 – Imago, photo in nature: *Endromis versicolora*, ♀, Yashkino, 21.04.2020, photo by V.A. Akaev; 26 – Imago, photo in nature: *Mimas tiliae*, Yashkino, 20.06.2010, photo by V.A. Akaev; 27 – Imago, photo in nature: *Choerocampa porcellus*, Yashkino, 12.06.2010, photo by V.A. Akaev.

Conclusion

Thus, 16 species of the Lasiocampidae family, one species from the Brahmaeidae family and one Endromididae species, 2 species of Saturniidae and 16 species of Sphingidae are reported to the fauna of the Kemerovo Region.

This list is not final and will certainly be supplemented with other species after systematic faunal studies are carried out in the studied area. For example, findings of such species as *Phyllodesma tremulifolium* (Hübner, 1810) is quite expected in the Kemerovo Region. This species is tend to steppe landscapes, but they often penetrate up to the northern forest-steppe zone through dry meadows (Knyazev 2020). In addition, the recently described Lappet moth *Phyllodesma yakovlevi* Zolotuhin, 2015, known from Altai and Tyva Republics (Zolotuhin 2015), is quite likely to be found in mountainous areas in Kemerovo Region.

Further targeted search for the listed species could increase the number of Lasiocampidae in the Kemerovo region up to 17–18 species. We also do not exclude the possibility of finding of *Lemonia taraxaci* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) in Kemerovo Region.

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